

METHODOLOGICAL OPPORTUNITIES FOR DEVELOPING A SENSE OF NATIONAL IDENTITY IN ADOLESCENTS THROUGH HISTORICAL KNOWLEDGE

G.B. Toremuratova

Independent Researcher, Ajiniyoz Nukus State Pedagogical Institute

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19435352>

Abstract. *This article discusses such structural models, consisting of the main structural elements of historical thinking, which are the basis for the development of a sense of self-awareness in students by providing them with historical knowledge, the dynamics of its development, features of historical thinking, the course of historical processes, its role in the development of students' point of view and imagination.*

Keywords: *national identity, value, education, historical thinking, historical knowledge, legends, communication, modeling.*

Introduction

The category of historical thinking serves as a key mechanism in the methodology of developing a sense of national identity among adolescent students through historical knowledge. In developed countries around the world, a number of international studies aimed at fostering students' awareness of national identity through historical knowledge are carried out on the basis of such approaches as historical thinking, historical empathy, civic education and national-civic identity, multicultural and intercultural education, as well as heritage-based education.

In a study conducted by Teresa Maresh, the differences between knowing history and historical thinking were examined. The author, relying on the views of Polish scholars such as O.M. Medushevskaya, B. Miskevich, Jerzy Topolski, S. Kossyalkovsky, and G. Labuda, analyzes the concept of "thinking" in this context. This article discusses how the presentation of historical knowledge to students can contribute to the development of their sense of identity, focusing on historical thinking, its developmental dynamics, its defining features, the nature of historical processes, and its role in shaping students' perspectives and imagination.

According to the author, historical thinking and historical knowledge are interrelated in a reciprocal manner. That is, historical thinking is formed on the basis of historical knowledge, while historical knowledge is acquired through the presence of historical thinking. Expressed in terms of mathematical logic, historical knowledge manifests itself on the basis of numerous instances of historical thinking. Accordingly, the concept of "historical thinking" is broader than the notion of "historical knowledge."

In scientific and methodological literature, based on the ideas of I. Gittis and I. Lerner, a structural model of historical thinking—one that remains relevant to this day—has been proposed. This model includes the following core components: the application of historical facts and events; the understanding that historical events and phenomena are interconnected and grounded in a certain chronology; the recognition of cause-and-effect relationships that reveal similarities and differences; the comprehension of the regularity of these relationships; the presence of the idea of

staged or phased development; and the systematization of multiple historical facts within the framework of a single historical event.

In the glossary of historical concepts titled “Historical Thinking,” the key concept is defined as follows: a set of mental processes underlying cognitive activity associated with the modeling of historical reality in the course of socio-cultural communication, based on language and information about it.

In their research, D.I. Ulbutov and N.S. Krot attempt to determine the levels of historical thinking formed among senior students of general secondary schools. For this purpose, the authors develop criteria for assessing the degree of its formation based on the following indicators of historical thinking: understanding the progressive development of historical processes through mastery of the concept of “historical time”; correlating historical phenomena with contemporary historical events; bringing diverse historical objects, which do not share the same status, to a common basis by generalizing their developmental processes; increasing the significance of characteristic features (stereotypes) that exist or previously existed when interpreting historical facts (i.e., generalizing historical representations under common labels); understanding dialogue (interconnectedness) between different cultures; comprehending the dynamic nature of historical phenomena (in general, the dialectic of individuality); verifying the reliability of historical facts through reference to primary sources; relying on rationality (their validity and correctness) and pragmatism (the idea of describing historical realities according to their external connections and consistency) in accepting historical facts; substantiating the development of historical processes based on both emotional and logical reasoning; recognizing the dynamic interrelation between subjective and objective aspects of historical phenomena; and applying the dialectics of comparing contradictory events in order to identify the logical proportionality between historical processes.

According to the Italian author’s approach, myths are neither falsehoods nor merely invented ideas; rather, they serve as a key to understanding not the surrounding nature itself, but the forms that express the lives of ancient people and the functions of their consciousness. Myths represent a specific organizational form of time and space through which it becomes possible to obtain knowledge about early human society and its representatives, as they constitute one of the primary sources of such information.

Ideas that we now consider absurd merely reflect our lack of understanding of the past. If we were able to comprehend the unique poetic lyricism of the creators of these myths, their seeming irrationality would disappear. Myths, in fact, can provide evidence about truth and reality that is no less grounded and reliable than that offered by modern scientific disciplines.

In a study conducted by M.A. Kissel, it is shown that for Giambattista Vico, myths are products of archaic (ancient) consciousness that convey information about the distant past of human history. The author cites Vico’s following idea on this matter: “Early humans were like the children of the human race; therefore, they were not capable of representing objects and phenomena in the way modern intellectuals do. Consequently, they were naturally compelled to express them through certain images or in forms close to idealized portraits—poetically, in a fantastic or universal manner.”

Indeed, myths constitute one of the essential foundations that significantly contribute to the formation of historical knowledge. Therefore, they contain, to a certain extent, elements of historical truth. The creator of myths is the people themselves; thus, they are regarded as a form of collective creative expression. As a unique synthesis of ideas, beliefs, and perceptions belonging

to the masses, myths embody certain truths related to the historical past of a particular ethnic group, nation, or people.

This, in turn, suggests that in general secondary education, integrating history teaching with national literature can be highly beneficial, enabling students to use myths as a distinctive type of primary historical source. At the same time, the study of myths helps develop students' professional competencies, such as analyzing the essence of historical events and phenomena, examining the social, economic, and cultural factors characteristic of a particular period, searching for additional historical evidence, and providing well-grounded interpretations.

The issue of historical thinking and its development in an individual is one of the most ancient problems and has been studied since the earliest periods when the category of thinking itself began to be explored. For instance, the ancient Greek philosopher Socrates paid particular attention to the study of historical memory in his philosophy. According to the philosopher, historical memory enables an individual to achieve self-awareness.

“Only a person who knows oneself clearly understands what is beneficial and what one is capable of. By engaging in activities within one's abilities, a person satisfies personal needs and attains well-being, avoiding errors and misfortunes. As a result, such a person is able to value others and make use of them for good purposes, ultimately protecting oneself from adversity.”

In the monograph *“Theoretical Foundations of the Philosophy of History”* by N.J. Jurayev, it is emphasized that knowledge of history is a decisive factor in the formation of national identity. Indeed, “self-awareness, first and foremost, begins with the study of the past and the need to know history. In fact, every person who seeks to understand oneself strives to learn about one's origins—where one was born, who one's ancestors were, what occupations they pursued, and how they lived. Such a person lives with pride in their virtues and heritage. Historical thinking and historical memory are formed in this very way.”

The ideas advanced in the research of Y.V. Slominskaya complement the views of Jo'rayev and further confirm the increasing importance of historical knowledge in the context of today's complex geopolitical processes. “In the conditions of the complex geopolitical processes occurring in the world, the study of historical knowledge is extremely important. It makes it possible to form a coherent system of economic, political, and philosophical views, and teaches the younger generation to think independently and broadly, avoiding one-sided judgments and conclusions that lack objectivity. Historical knowledge enables us to look into the future through the prism of the past.”

In his research, G.B. Khojametov focuses on the problem of using ICT to enhance the effectiveness of teaching history. According to the author, in modern conditions, it is possible to achieve greater efficiency in teaching history through the creation of a virtual museum using ICT tools. In this regard, the following stages for developing a virtual museum are outlined:

1. Introducing students to the functional capabilities of Visme and Netlify, which allow them to create and present a virtual museum, and demonstrating the importance of using these tools for didactic purposes.
2. Collecting photographic materials on the topic “Ancient States in the Territory of Central Asia.”
3. Selecting, systematizing, and categorizing the collected materials.
4. Forming sections of the virtual museum based on topics assigned to small groups and providing explanatory descriptions for each section.

5. Presenting the theoretical descriptions, photographs, and texts in a visual format using the Visme and Netlify platforms.

Indeed, the development of modern education cannot be imagined without the influence of ICT. Today, in teaching history, the use of contemporary teaching tools such as virtual museums, virtual excursions, virtual galleries, interactive presentations, e-posters, and online dictionaries helps enhance teaching effectiveness.

In the research conducted by Kh.K. Boymirzayev, the object of study was the process of improving history teaching methodology within an innovative educational environment. The study identified the effectiveness of graphic organizers such as “Thesis Organizer,” “Cognitive Map,” and “Morphological Box” in enhancing the teaching of history.

Furthermore, it has been established that in teaching the subject “*History of Uzbekistan*”, computer technologies such as PowerPoint, Hot Potatoes, as well as the Visme and Netlify platforms, can be used to create interactive posters that effectively organize the learning process. These tools facilitate thorough mastery of learning materials by students, allow monitoring of their educational activities, and serve to assess the level of knowledge and skills acquired.

Conclusion

In developing a sense of national identity among adolescent students through historical knowledge, international studies in developed countries, along with research conducted to reform the national education system, emphasize approaches based on historical thinking, historical empathy, civic education and national-civic identity, and heritage-based learning. These studies highlight that the integration of such approaches in teaching serves as a foundation for scientific research in this field, taking into account modern methodological possibilities and contributing to the development of new contemporary educational technologies.

REFERENCES

1. Maresz, Teresa. *Historical Knowledge or Historical Thinking?* Translated from Polish by D.A. Dobrovolskii. Available at: https://roii.ru/publications/dialogue/article/44_7/marez_teresa/historical-knowledge-or-historical-thinking.
2. *Historical Consciousness of Russian Youth / Monograph*. Edited by S.V. Alekseev. – Moscow: Vlado, 2015. – p. 18.
3. *Historical Thinking // Theory and Methodology of Historical Science: Terminological Dictionary* / Ed. by A.O. Chubaryan. – Moscow: 2014. – pp. 311–313.
4. Ulbutov, D.I., & Krot, N.S. Determining Historical Analogies as an Indicator of the Formation of Historical Thinking in Senior Students // *Pedagogy and Psychology of Education*. – Moscow: 2019, No. 1. – pp. 89–90.
5. Gubin, V.D., & Strelkov, V.I. *The Power of History: Essays on the History of the Philosophy of History / Lecture Course*. – Moscow: RGGU, 2007. – p. 114.
6. Medvedev, O. *Giambattista Vico (1668–1744)*. Available at: http://me.hse.ru/noncanonical-philosophy/results2021/giambattista_vico.
7. Gubin, V.D., & Strelkov, V.I. *The Power of History: Essays on the History of the Philosophy of History / Lecture Course*. – Moscow: RGGU, 2007. – p. 63.
8. Slominskaya, E.V. Methodological Features of Teaching History in Technical Universities // *Modern Problems of Science and Education*, 2014, No. 6. – p. 34.

9. Khojametov, G.B. Increasing the Effectiveness of Using ICT in Teaching History (Using the Example of Teaching the Subject “*History Teaching Methodology*”: PhD in Pedagogical Sciences, Philosophy) – Nukus: 2023. – pp. 16–17.
10. Boymirzayev, Kh.K. Improving the Methodology of Teaching History in an Innovative Educational Environment (Using the Example of the Subject “*History of Statehood in Uzbekistan*”: Doctor of Philosophy in Pedagogical Sciences) – Namangan: 2022. – p. 103.